

MOLECULAR DETERMINANTS OF ANTIFUNGAL RESISTANCE IN *CANDIDA AURIS*

Bazarova Gulnora Rustamovna

Associate Professor at the “Alfraganus “ university’s medical faculty

Email: gulnorabazarova599@gmail.com

Orcid Id: 0009-0006-7621-2642

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14564476>

Abstract

Candida auris is known for its strains resistant to multiple antifungal agents, prompting research into the molecular mechanisms underlying this resistance. This review aims to summarize key findings from recent studies. A comprehensive search of online databases and relevant websites was conducted. The analysis reveals that most *C. auris* strains exhibit high resistance to fluconazole, moderate resistance to amphotericin B, and lower resistance to 5-fluorocytosine and caspofungin. Amphotericin B resistance in *C. auris* has been linked to the overexpression of mutated ERG genes, resulting in reduced ergosterol levels. Resistance to fluconazole is largely attributed to mutations in the ERG11 gene, an increased number of ERG11 gene copies, and overexpression of efflux pumps. For 5-fluorocytosine, resistance is hypothesized to stem from mutations in the FCY2, FCY1, and FUR1 genes. Caspofungin resistance is associated with mutations in the FKS1 gene. Moreover, resistance to each antifungal appears to be closely related to the clade type of the *C. auris* strain.

Keywords: antifungal resistance, *Candida auris*, amphotericin B, 5-fluorocytosine, caspofungin, fluconazole.

Introduction

Candida auris is a globally significant pathogen, known for its resistance to nearly all antifungal agents commonly used to treat invasive fungal infections. It poses a severe threat to human health, particularly in Intensive Care Unit (ICU) settings, where life-threatening outbreaks of candidiasis have been reported. In several countries, *C. auris* is now recognized as a major public health concern.

Since its discovery in 2009, *C. auris* has rapidly spread worldwide. Initial isolates were reported in Japan, India, Pakistan, South Africa, and Venezuela. To date, its presence has been documented in 19 additional countries across six continents.

Phylogenetic studies on the genomes of various *C. auris* isolates have identified four predominant populations, referred to as clades I, II, III, and IV. Evidence of a smaller population, likely representing a fifth clade (clade V), has been linked to an isolate obtained from the otic exudate of a girl in Iran. While clades I through IV exhibit a wide geographical distribution, clade V remains less frequently isolated.

The rapid territorial expansion of *C. auris* is partly attributed to misidentification using phenotypic characterization methods, which have often confused it with *C. haemulonii*, *C. famata*, *C. catenulata*, or even *Rhodotorula glutinis*. These misidentifications have delayed the implementation of preventive measures to control its spread.

The multi-drug resistance of *C. auris* is likely related to its phylogenetic relationship with other *Candida* species that are inherently resistant to multiple antifungal agents.

Materials and Methods

This review aims to provide updated insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying the antifungal resistance characteristic of most *Candida auris* strains. To achieve this, a comprehensive search was conducted across multiple platforms, including ScienceDirect, Springer Link, Wiley Online Library, and Medline (PubMed). The keywords used were *Candida auris* antifungal resistance.

The search initially yielded 4,518 publications. After excluding 4,415 articles that were either irrelevant to the topic or in languages difficult to translate, a total of 102 articles were selected for inclusion. These articles were published between 2000 and 2020, with one additional article from 1994 included for its historical significance. The review process adhered to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis) guidelines to ensure a systematic and comprehensive approach.

Polyenes

The polyene class of antifungals includes amphotericin B (AMB), nystatin, and natamycin. Unlike AMB and nystatin, natamycin interacts with ergosterol without forming ion channels, instead affecting ergosterol-dependent processes that precede membrane fusion.

In most *Candida* species, resistance to polyenes is rare, except for species like *C. lusitanae*. However, resistance can develop due to prophylactic or therapeutic exposure. It has also been hypothesized that prior azole treatment may reduce ergosterol levels, leading to subsequent polyene resistance. Genome sequencing of *C. auris* has identified mutations in the ERG11 gene, such as F126T, Y132F, and K143F, associated with different geographic clades. These findings suggest that *C. auris* antifungal resistance may be acquired rather than intrinsic.

Regarding polyene susceptibility, particularly AMB, studies show variable results. While *C. auris* generally exhibits resistance to AMB after fluconazole, susceptibility rates vary. For example, one study demonstrated low susceptibility, with 50% of isolates showing elevated minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs). Resistance rates to AMB among *C. auris* isolates range between 10% and 35% in various studies. For instance, a U.S. study found two-thirds of isolates were resistant, while another study reported resistance in only one of seven isolates. In a systematic review, 15.46% of *C. auris* isolates were resistant to AMB, a finding consistent with other studies using CDC-defined cut-off points. Regional variations also exist; for instance, in Kuwait, resistance rates increased significantly when alternative MIC references were applied.

Comparatively, species closely related to *C. auris*, such as *C. haemulonii*, *C. duobushaemulonii*, and *C. pseudohaemulonii*, show high intrinsic resistance to AMB, with MICs reaching up to 16 mg/L. Acquired resistance has also been observed in other *Candida* species, including *C. albicans*, *C. glabrata*, *C. lusitanae*, and *C. tropicalis*, with cases of pan-resistance reported in *C. auris*.

The molecular mechanisms underlying AMB resistance in *C. auris* remain unclear. However, disruptions in the ergosterol biosynthesis pathway, likely linked to mutations in genes such as ERG2, ERG3, and ERG6, are believed to play a central role. These mutations may lead to reduced or altered ergosterol levels, increasing resistance. In resistant *C. auris* strains, overexpression of genes including ERG1, ERG2, ERG3, ERG5, ERG6, and ERG13 has been observed. Reduced ergosterol levels in the plasma membrane directly correlate with increased AMB resistance.

Some studies suggest that antifungal resistance in *C. auris* may also involve transcriptional regulation. For example, research comparing AMB-resistant and susceptible strains has indicated overexpression of ergosterol pathway genes at the transcriptional level, reinforcing the complexity of resistance mechanisms.

Triazoles

Triazoles are widely used antifungal agents effective in disrupting fungal plasma membrane formation, making them a key treatment option against infections caused by various *Candida* species. However, their extensive use has led to host side effects and the emergence of resistance in pathogens.

In *Candida auris*, triazole resistance primarily involves three mechanisms: (1) mutations in the target gene ERG11, (2) overexpression of ERG11, and (3) overregulation of efflux pumps. Resistance is most commonly observed with fluconazole, while it is less frequent for other triazoles like voriconazole. Phylogenetic evidence suggests that triazole resistance has independently evolved at least four times, likely driven by the widespread use of antifungals as prophylactic and therapeutic agents for nosocomial infections. The consistent availability of fluconazole further accelerates resistance by inducing rapid mutations.

The ERG11 gene, which encodes lanosterol-14 α -demethylase (the target protein for triazoles' fungistatic action), is among the most studied in relation to *C. auris* resistance. To date, 12 mutations in the ERG11 gene have been identified, many of which appear to be geographically distinct. These mutations reduce the binding affinity between triazoles and their target, diminishing fungal susceptibility to the drugs. As a result, susceptibility patterns to triazoles vary depending on the strain's geographic origin.

The evolutionary pressure exerted by frequent antifungal use underscores the complexity of managing triazole resistance in *C. auris* and highlights the need for region-specific strategies to mitigate its spread.

Conclusions

Candida auris has emerged as a global public health concern due to the increasing prevalence of multi-resistant strains across various antifungal groups, significantly limiting therapeutic options. It has been suggested that the *C. auris* genome has adapted to resist antifungal agents in response to the indiscriminate use of broad-spectrum antibiotics and antifungals, similar to the resistance seen with triazoles, particularly in marginalized populations. The study of molecular resistance mechanisms is further complicated by the genetic variability among *C. auris* clades, which influences resistance profiles. For example, polyene resistance varies by geographic region, and echinocandin-resistant strains have been reported in India and South Africa.

Current knowledge of *C. auris* molecular resistance mechanisms remains limited, but resistance is known to occur through mutations in genes such as ERG2, ERG3, ERG6, ERG11, and FKS1, overexpression of efflux pump genes, and single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in various genomic loci. While polyenes can be effective against *C. auris*, their efficacy may be enhanced when used in combination with other antifungals such as 5-fluorocytosine (5-FC). Although not a first-line treatment, 5-FC shows potential when paired with polyenes, echinocandins, or azoles.

Despite its wide distribution and association with high mortality rates, *C. auris* remains underexplored. It is critical to deepen our understanding of its resistance mechanisms and

investigate additional molecular factors contributing to its tolerance and resistance to antifungals. Such research is essential for developing novel and more effective treatment options against this emerging pathogen.

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